

Fig. S4. CPN20 peptide is O-fucosylated in an *in vitro* SPY activity assay.

(A) ETD MS2 spectrum of synthesized CPN20 peptide $\text{KIDITVPTGAQIIYS}^{\text{O-fucose}}\text{K}$.

(B) ETD MS2 spectrum of synthesized CPN20 peptide $\text{KIDITVPT}^{\text{O-fucose}}\text{GAQIIYSK}$.

The CPN20 peptide reacted with GDP-fucose and 3TPR-SPY in the reaction buffer for 8 h at 25 ° C before analyzed by ETD-MS/MS.